

The Perspectives of Adolescents with Disclosed HIV Status on Disclosure in Bamenda Health District in the North West Region of Cameroon.

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ABSTRACT.

Disclosure is a process of telling an adolescent that he or she has HIV and helping him or her to understand what this means. It has always been a very difficult task for most parents since they don't know what and how to tell the child and also because they find it very difficult to tell them the truth about their condition. This has led to low disclosure rates and a consequent abandonment of treatment by these children (adolescents) with a subsequent increase in viral load and a rapid spread of the disease. **Objective:** To analyze the perspectives of adolescents with disclosed HIV status on disclosure. **Methods:** this study was a cross-sectional study carried out from June 2023 to September 2023 in the Bamenda Health District. The target population was made up of 120 adolescents with disclosed HIV status, who are on antiretroviral therapy in 6 different sampled health areas. Data was collected using questionnaires. It was analyzed using SPSS. **Results:** Adolescents want to be told the truth about their condition. They prefer that disclosure should be done at 12 years because they are eager to know why they are taking medications on a daily basis, and also because they do not want to remain in the dark for long. Majority of them prefer to be disclosed to in the health facility and by health workers because the health facility is an environment that makes the information to look real, and the health workers usually tell them the truth. **Conclusion:** This study revealed that adolescents will like to be told the truth concerning their disease. They will not like to remain in the dark for long. They prefer to be disclosed to at 12 years, as this promotes adherence to antiretroviral therapy (ART) and safer sex practices.

Key words: adolescents, ART, adherence, safe sex, perspectives, disclosure, truth, Bamenda Health District.

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INTRODUCTION

Generally adolescent refers to people in their second decade of life, meaning those between the ages of 10 to 19 years. Adolescents with disclosed HIV status are those whose disease condition has been disclosed to them, and now they know why they are on antiretroviral therapy. Not much has been published on the perspectives of disclosure among adolescents with disclosed status. The World Health Organization recommends full disclosure of HIV positive status to adolescents who acquire HIV prenatally by the age of 12 years (1). Making HIV infected children aware of the HIV status is an issue of great concern for public health, partly because of the many proven benefits it brings for mental health, psychosocial development, caregiver wellbeing, treatment adherence and future planning (2). Care givers /parents consider 12 years as being too young for disclosure (3). Data from research surveillance and program monitoring has shown that HIV infected adolescents have lower rates of knowing their HIV status (4). This can lead to treatment abandonment and an increase in the spread of the disease (5). Analyzing the perspectives of adolescents on disclosure, we found that, adolescents would like to be disclosed to at 12 years of age (6). Adolescents prefer early disclosure performed in a health care setting (7, 8). Adolescents have a preference for disclosure by the health care provider because they had an opportunity for more accurate biomedical information and could cope better with the disease than information received from their caregivers alone (9). More disclosure by health care providers or caregivers to infected adolescents directly will encourage safer sexual behaviors that. The WHO guidelines on disclosure counseling to children under 12 years of age indicated that there is no evidence for either health care provider or caregivers disclosure but emphasized that disclosure should be in the best interest of the child (10). Despite the benefits of disclosure, majority of parents/caregivers delay disclosure and prefer that it should be done after 12 years, which is not in line with the WHO guidelines (11).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A qualitative study was carried out in 6 health facilities within the Bamenda 1 health District, from the June 2022 to September 2023. This survey targeted adolescents that were on ART, and knew their HIV status, and who attended clinic in the different HIV treatment Centers. The materials

that were used were questionnaires. To assess the perspectives of adolescents, on disclosure. A purposive random sampling was done to choose the major HIV treatment center in Bamenda 1 health district.

An authorization was gotten from the administrators of the different HIV treatment centers. During the data collection process, a volunteer health worker within the HIV treatment unit accepted to screen the adolescents that were eligible for the survey. We were given a room where we sat inside with the adolescent and administered the questionnaire. Those eligible were the adolescents that were on ART and that had been disclosed, i.e. they had been told that they have HIV.

This work was carried out in the Bamenda 1 health district of the North West Region of Cameroon. Bamenda 1 health district is made up of 10 health areas, namely; Atuakom, Ntambag, Mendankwe, Mbachongwa, Alamandom, Mankon, Ntankah, Mulang, Alamandom, and Azire. It share borders with the following health districts; to the East it shares borders with Bamenda 3 and Tubah health districts, to the South with Santa and Bali health districts, to the west it shares borders with Mbengwi health district and to the North with Bafut health district. it was carried out in some sampled treatment centers namely, Bamenda Regional Hospital, Azire integrated health Center, Atuakom Integrated Health Center, Saint Mary Soledad Alakuma and the peoples clinic Atuakum. Amongst these HIV treatment was one of the biggest HIV treatment Centers within the Bamenda 1 Health district of the North West Region of Cameroon which is the Bamenda Regional Hospital. Adolescents who are aware of their HIV status also have access to a peer support group of adolescents with disclosed status. This peer support is for adolescents with disclosed status who are between 14 years to 19years. The study population was adolescents with disclosed HIV status: These are individuals 10 to 19 years in sampled HIV treatment centers of the Bamenda 1 health district that have been disclosed to. The adolescents that were included were, adolescents that are on ART, and know their HIV status, and are attaining clinic in the sampled HIV treatment centers within the Bamenda health district that accepted to take part in this research. Meanwhile, adolescents that are on ART and know their HIV status, and are attaining clinic in the sampled health facilities within the Bamenda health district and that did not accept to take part in this research were excluded. To calculate the sample size we used the Yamane's formula. Both the probability and non-probability methods of sampling were involved. We started with a purposive

sampling method, which is a non-probability method of sampling, wherein, the most prominent and biggest HIV treatment Center within the Bamenda Health district was identified and selected. This was the Bamenda Regional Hospital. This was followed by a simple random sampling method which is a probability method of sampling, wherein the names of all the 10 health areas within the Bamenda 1 health district were attributed arbitrary numbers. The numbers were then written down on pieces of papers and folded in such a way that they were not visible. Then a child was asked to pick 4 umbers out of the lot. These 4 numbers corresponded to four health areas within the Bamenda 1 health district. Namely; AZIRE, Ntambag, Atuakom, and Mankon health areas respectively. Then a purposive sampling was done to identify the most prominent HIV treatment Centers within the sampled health areas. The following HIV treatment centers were identified namely, Saint Blaise Clinic, Foundation Clinic Atuakom, Saint Mary Soledad Clinic, Azire imtegrated health Center and Atuakom Integrated Health Center. These were added to the most prominent and biggest HIV treatment Center within the Bamenda 1 Health district which had earlier been identified using the purposive sampling technique at the very beginning, this gave us 6 HIV treatment Centers within the Bamenda 1 health district In order for us to access the data in the different HIV treatment Centers, we applied for authorization to carry out the data, and waited for it to be granted.

The administrators of the different sampled HIV treatment Centers led us to the HIV treatment units and introduced us to the personnel working there. We used the HIV treatment Registers to count the number of adolescents that have already been disclosed to, and the total number of adolescents who were on antiretroviral therapy but who had not yet been disclosed to, and then we noted the figures according to their ages; adolescents 10 to 15 years and adolescents 15 to 19years. These figures were written down in our jotters, to be used subsequently in calculating our sample size for the survey.

We used the Yamane's formula to calculate the simple size for the survey as follows;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where

n= sample size

N= population size

e= margin error (0.05)

$$n = \frac{131}{1 + 131(0.05)^2}$$

$$(0.05)^2 = 0.0025$$

$$1 + 131(0.0025) = 1.3275$$

$n = \frac{131}{1.3275} = 98.68 = 99$ which was rounded up to 100 being the least sample size, so our sample size was 120

Furthermore, we used questionnaires to collect data on the perspectives of HIV Disclosure by adolescents with disclosed status, this was achieved with the aid of a volunteer health worker. This volunteer health worker identified the adolescents that were eligible for the study. These were adolescents that were on antiretroviral therapy and had been disclosed to and that consented to take part in the study. The questionnaires were self-administered in one of the offices within the HIV treatment Center. This provided privacy to the participants and gave room for them to open up and give us correct answers, because nobody was allowed to enter the office during the time of administration of the questionnaire. In some days we had just one participant that was eligible.

The questionnaires comprised of both open and close ended questions. Data was entered and analyzed using SPSS. We got ethical clearance from the University of Bamenda, followed by an authorization from the Regional Delegation of Public Health and then authorization from the different sampled health facilities in Bamenda 1.

RESULTS

Perspectives of adolescents with disclosed status on disclosure

Socio-demographic information

A total of 120 adolescents were interviewed accordingly. The age of the adolescents ranges from 12-19 year old, with the Mean age of 17.18. There were more females with HIV positive status (63%) than the males (37%). Those with highest education were those in secondary school (45%). This corresponds to the mean age, which is the age at which most of those adolescents are in secondary school. Closely followed were those in primary schools, which correspond to the age group from 12 to 14 years. The result shows that majority of the adolescents were living with their parents (60%), followed by those living with other family members (37%). some of the caregiver's educational status were not known (37.5%). Those whose educational status was known, most of them had completed just primary school (23%).

Table i: Socio-demographic information

Variable (n=120)	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	45	37.5
Female	75	62.5
Highest Education		
Primary	45	37.5
Secondary school	54	45.0
High School	12	10.0
Still in the University	19	7.5
Person the child live with		
Parent	72	60.0
Family member	45	37.5
Friend	3	2.5
Education of primary caregiver		
Completed primary school	27	22.5
Completed secondary school	18	15.0
Completed high school	9	7.5
Completed university/higher school	21	17.5
Do not know	45	37.5

Experiences of adolescents on HIV disclosure

Based on the experiences of adolescents as shown on **Table ii**, most of the disclosed status were done by the healthcare providers (35%), followed by those disclosed by their mothers (25.0%). In that light, most of the disclosures were done at the health facility (57.5%). Most disclosures were done incrementally (That is, it took some time, with sessions among other peers(45.0%) as well as with basic simple, clear age –appropriate facts, explained in a language that the children could understand (37.5%).

Table ii: Experiences of adolescents on HIV disclosure

Variable (n=120)	Frequency	Percentage
Person that disclosed your status to you		
Parent (Both parent)	18	15.0
Mother	30	25.0
Father	12	10.0
Guardians	18	15.0
Healthcare provider	42	35.0
Place of disclosure		
At home	48	40.0
In a health facility	69	57.5
On my sick bed	3	2.5
Method it was disclosed		
Incrementally (it took some time, we were having sessions with other peers)	54	45.0
It was given in small volumes and repeated frequently	18	15.0
I was given simple, basic, clear age –appropriate facts, explained in a language that I could understand	45	37.5
It was not given in small volumes	3	2.5

Reactions of adolescents following disclosure

For emotional reaction to the disclosed status, some of the adolescents were very sad (35.0%). while others were angry (17.5%). Only 30% were ready for such result, while majority of them were not ready for such information disclosed to them (70%).

Table iii: Reactions of adolescents following disclosure

Variable (n=120)	frequency	percentage
Reactions following disclosure		
I was happy to know my HIV seropositive status	12	10.0
I was very sad	78	65.0
I was very angry	68	56.6
I was calm	24	20.0
I was shocked	70	58.3
I thought of committing suicide	3	2.5
I was anxious of dying soon	81	67.5
Readiness for the results	84	70.0
Not ready	36	30.0
Ready		
Reason for not being ready	84	70.0
I never thought I could ever have such a disease		
Reason for being ready	36	30.0
I suspected that I had HIV		

Existential perspectives of adolescents following disclosure

The results on **table iii** show that majority of them were not ready for the disclosure of their HIV seropositive status (.70.0%) meanwhile, some of them were ready for the disclosure (30%) as they thought that they will be able to live a normal life.(12,5%), they will be able to live positively(10.0%) and could even live longer(7,5%).

After disclosure, some of them felt that they will be unable to live a normal live (40.0%),

Some of them thought that they were not the only person living with HIV (30.0%), while most of them thought that they were the only ones living with HIV (70.0%). Most of them (70.0%) were not very comfortable concerning HIV and medication, HIV is incurable, while some still trusted the effectiveness of the medicine (19.0%). Most of them also felt that they would be stigmatized (70.0%).

Table IV: Existential perspectives of adolescents following disclosure

Variable (n=120)	Frequency	Percentage
Existential perspectives when your HIV seropositive status was disclosed to you		
I will be unable to live a normal life	48	40.0
I will be able to live as normal	15	12.5
I will be able to live positively	12	10.0
I will live longer	9	7.5
I was anxious about dying soon	81	67.5%
Self-image after disclosure		
I thought that I was the only person living with HIV	84	70.0
I knew that I was not the only person living with HIV	36	30.0
Opinion on HIV and medication		
Didn't want to take medicine daily for the rest of my life	70	58.0
I was concerned about dependency on the medicine	13	11.0
I trusted the effectiveness of the medicine	23	19.0
HIV is incurable or a bad disease	14	12.0
I continued taking my medications	106	88.3
Stigmatization after disclosure		
I anticipated that I will be stigmatized	84	70.0
I did not think of being stigmatized	36	30.0

Perspectives of adolescents on the impact of disclosure on their behaviour

Despite the disappointment upon disclosure, majority of the adolescent reported that they continued taking their medications (88.3%), while a few stopped taking the medications for some time (11.6%). After disclosure, some felt more comfortable talking about HIV with their parents (28.3%), while most of them were more comfortable talking about HIV with the health workers (66.6%). Upon disclosure, most of the adolescents became scared of developing intimate relationships (57.5%), while some isolated themselves from friends (40.0%).

Table V: Perspectives of adolescents on the impact of disclosure on their behaviour

Variable (n=120)	Frequency	Percentage
The impact of disclosure of HIV seropositive status on your emotions and behavior		
I stopped taking my medications for some time	14	11.6
I continued taking my medications	106	88.3

Your impact on disclosure regarding relationships with parents or primary care givers as a consequence of disclosure

I felt more comfortable talking about HIV with health workers	80	66.6
I did not tell others my status	40	33.3
I felt more comfortable talking about HIV with my parents	34	28.3
I blamed my parents	28	23.3

Your impact on disclosure regarding relationships with friends or intimate partners as a consequence of disclosure

I practiced safe sex	21	17.5
I became scared of developing intimate relationships	69	57.5
I isolated myself from friends	48	40.0
I stopped sexual relationship	32	26.6

Perspectives of adolescents on satisfaction/non-satisfaction following disclosure.

Most of them were not satisfied with the disclosure (70.0%), because they never knew that they could ever be HIV positive and as such were not ready for such results (70.0%), while few were satisfied with the disclosure (30.0%) because they had been prepared and so accepted it.

Table vi: Perspectives of adolescents on satisfaction/non-satisfaction following disclosure

Variable(n=100)	frequency	percentage
Satisfaction/non-satisfaction following the disclosure		
Was satisfied with the disclosure	36	30.0
Was not satisfied with the disclosure	84	70.0
Reasons for satisfaction		
I had been prepared and so I accepted it	36	30.0
Reasons for non- satisfaction with the disclosure		
I never knew that I could ever be HIV positive, so I was not ready for such results	84	70.0

Perspectives of adolescents on onward disclosure

some of the adolescents who knew about their HIV seropositive had not told anybody about it (70.0%), while 30.0% has told others.. those that had not told anybody said that their reasons for not telling others was because was because, they were ashamed (60.0%) and were also afraid of stigma and discrimination(62,0%). Some of them were satisfied after telling somebody (33.0%) because they were encouraged and supported (22.0%).

Table vii: perspectives of adolescents on onward disclosure

Variable (n=120)	Frequency	Percentage
Have ever told anybody about your HIV status		
Have not told anybody	84	70.0
Have told somebody or others	36	30.0
Persons told		
Family members	20	17.0
friend	16	13.0
Reasons for not telling anybody		
I don't trust people	80	66.0
I am afraid of stigma and discrimination	75	62.0
I am ashamed	73	60.0
Satisfaction following disclosure to others by adolescents		
Satisfied	31	26.0
Not satisfied	5	4.0
Reason for satisfaction		
I was encouraged and supported	25	21.0
It improved on my psychological wellbeing	23	19.0
It enhanced my physical health	20	14.0
Non satisfaction/reasons		
It brought about stigmatization	11	9.0
	5	4.0

Perspectives of adolescents on the perceived advantages and disadvantages of disclosure

Majority of the adolescents perceive that disclosure was important because; it provides them with the reason for taking medicine everyday (83.0%), it also improves adherence to ART (82.5%), it prevents the transmission of HIV (67.0%), It is their basic right (75.0%) and it also enhances self-

care (42.0%). For disadvantages, some of them said that they were not ready and prepared for the results (33.0%). while some disclosed their status unnecessarily to others (27.0%).

Table viii: perspectives of adolescents on disclosure readiness and the perceived advantages, disadvantages of disclosure

Variable (n=120)	Frequency	Percentage
Perceived advantages of disclosure		
It is important to know the reason for taking medicine everyday	100	83.0
It improves adherence ART	99	82.5
It is important to prevent HIV transmission	80	67.0
It is my basic right	90	75.0
It enhances self-care	60	42.0
Disadvantages of disclosure		
I disclosed my status unnecessarily to others	32	27.0
I was not ready and prepared for the results	40	33.0
I was emotionally distressed	21	18.0
I was discouraged about taking medications	6	5.0

Topics taught in preparation for disclosure

Some topics that were taught in preparation for disclosure were; Benefits of adherence (33%). Risk of non-adherence (13.0%), general modes of HIV transmission (58.0%), and how to deal with emotions (24.0%) and how to develop hope for the future (16.0%), and duration of taking antiretroviral therapy once it begins (8.0%).

Table ix: topics taught in preparation for disclosure and the preferred age for disclosure

The following topics taught to you before disclosure of your seropositive status

Variable(n=120)	frequency	percentage
Benefits of adherence	37	30.8
General modes of HIV transmission	70	58.3
how to deal with emotions	29	24.1
Risk of non-adherence	15	12.5
How to develop hope for the future	19	15.8

Duration of taking ART once it begins 10 8.3

Perspectives of adolescents on the preferred age of disclosure

51.0 % of adolescents preferred to be disclosed to at the age of 12years

Table X preferred age of disclosure

Preferred age of disclosure

Variable (n=120)	frequency	percentage
10	8	6.6
12	62	51.6
13	18	15.0
14	9	7.5
15	12	10.0
17	6	5.0
18	5	4.1

Experience on peer support groups

Concerning peer support group, majority of the adolescents (80.0%) reported that there were peer support groups and 75.0% of them acknowledged that they were members of these support groups. Majority of them reported their satisfaction with the peer group support (71.0%). Most common reasons for the satisfaction with the peer support group were some financial support (71.0%) and education on HIV (50.0%) and other HIV related issues (42.5%)

Table x: Adolescent experiences on peer support groups

Variable (n=120)	Frequency	Percentage
Availability of peer support group		
There is	96	80.0
There is not	24	20.0
Membership in the group		
We are not	28	23.3
We are	92	76.6
Satisfaction with the adolescent peer support group		
Satisfied	85	70.8
Not satisfied	7	5.8
Reasons for satisfaction		
Improves adherence to treatment	83	69.1
Provides better coping strategies	51	42.5
At times they are therapeutic sessions	13	10.8
Explore HIV related issues	50	41.6
They give us some financial support	85	70.8
They help to reduce stigma and isolation	83	69.1
They encourage self –expression/self esteem	74	61.6
Educate us on HIV	60	50.0
Reasons for nonsatisfaction		
It is boring at times	7	5.8

Experiences on adolescent involvement

The majority of adolescent participants reported that they do participate in all decision that affect them (68.0%) and that they will be very satisfied if they always participate in all decisions that affect them (58.0%). The reason is that it enhances self- efficiency (57.0) and adherence to treatment (54.0%).

Table xi: Experiences on adolescent involvement in decision making

Variable (n=120)	Frequency	Percentage
Adolescent participation in decisions that affect them		
We do participate	81	67.5
We do not participate	39	32.5
Satisfaction/non-satisfaction with respect to adolescent participation in decision making		
Satisfied	70	58.3
Not satisfied	11	9.1
Reasons for satisfaction		
Enhances adherence to treatment	65	54.1
Enhances self-efficiency	68	56.6
Reasons for nonsatisfaction		
Not matured enough to take correct decisions	11	9.1

Adolescent perspectives on safe sex practices following disclosure

Some of them reported that after disclosure, they do not engage in any sexual activity (45.0%) out of the 73 of them that practice safe sex, 45 of them practice abstinence, while 13 of them always practice safe sex and 15 of them sometimes practice safe sex. Of the 73 of them that practice safe sex, 60 of them are satisfied while 13 of them are not satisfied practicing safe sex. The main reason for satisfaction being that, they do not want to spread the disease to others (80%). Most of them reported the challenge on how to use condom for safe sexual intercourse (61.5 %).

Adolescent perspectives on safe sex practices following disclosure

Safe sex practices after disclosure

Variable(n=120)	frequency	percentage
Always	21	17.5
Sometimes	12	10.0
Never	33	27.5
I do not have sex (abstinence)	54	45.0

Satisfaction practicing safe sex

We are satisfied	75	62.5
We are not satisfied	45	37.5

Reasons for satisfaction practicing safe sex

I don't want to re-infect myself	36	30.0
I don't want to spread the disease to others	68	56.6

Reasons for non-satisfaction in practicing safe sex

I don't know how to use a condom	36	30.0
I don't like to use a condom	12	10.0

Adolescent's perspectives on the preferred person and place of disclosure

Majority of the adolescents prefer to be disclosed to be health care providers (87.5%), reason being that the health workers know much about the disease and that they will tell them the truth. also 110 of them (91.6%) prefer to be disclosed to in health facility , reason being that the health facility looks more real, the health workers will tell them the right and correct information about the disease and they are more knowledgeable and skilled.

Adolescent’s perspectives on the preferred person and place of disclosure

Preferred person to do disclosure

Variable (n=120)	frequency	percentage
Health workers	105	87.5
Parents/caregivers	15	12,5

Reasons for disclosure by health workers

Health workers know much about the disease	105	87.5
Health workers will tell us the truth	100	83.3
Our parents usually lie to us	98	81.6

Preferred place of disclosure

Health facility	110	91.6
At home	10	8.3

Reason for the disclosure to be done at the health facility

Health facility looks more real	102	85.0
Health workers will tell us the right and correct information	108	90.0
Health workers are more knowledgeable and skilled	111	92.5

Discussion

Discussions on the perspectives of adolescents on disclosure

In this study, the ages ranged from 12 to 19 years with the mean age of 17.18, having more females than males, which is slightly different from another study where the ages ranged from 13 to 19 years with the mean age of 16.6. Both studies had adolescents as participants. Females were more than the males and their highest level of education being secondary school. In both studies, all the participants knew their HIV status (12). In this work, Adolescents reported that their status were disclosed to them by their mothers (22.0%). This is in line with the results obtained from a mixed study where adolescents reported that their status was disclosed to them by their mothers (29.5%). Disclosure by health care providers was found to be (35%) as opposed to (27.4%), by their father (10%) as opposed to 7.9% and by both parents (15%) as opposed to 62.5% in another study (13). This may be due to some cultural taboos within the Bamenda 1 health district, where talking to a child about sex issues is regarded as a taboo which makes fathers and parents to shy away from their responsibilities and shift it to the health care providers. Most disclosures were done incrementally (That is, it took some time, with sessions among other peers) (40%) as well as with basic simple, clear age –appropriate facts, explained in a language that the children could understand could (38.0%). This is in line with a systematic review carried out in SSA, which reported that disclosure was defined by mention of “HIV or AIDS” when explaining the illness to infected children and adolescents implying full disclosure. Otherwise partial disclosure is the case (14, 15, 16 and 17). Concerning emotional reaction following disclosure, some of the adolescents were very sad and depressed (35%), very angry (17.0%) shocked (20%) and thought of committing suicide (5.0%), and anxious about dying soon (34%), and thought that they are the only ones living with HIV(46.0%). which ties with a report from a thematic analysis which reported that they were emotionally shocked, and some desired to commit suicide, anxious about dying soon and a sense of isolation, as if being the only person living with HIV, and had a feeling of being stigmatized (18, 19). This study shows that majority of them were not ready for the results (70.0.0%) because they never knew that they could ever be HIV positive. While some of them were ready for the disclosure because they wanted to know why they were constantly sick (30.0%), which is in line with another study that reported that some had a positive impression about it (7.9%) while (45.3%)

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others had a negative impression because they never expected it (20). Commonly they are strongly distressed when they are informed about their HIV serostatus while some get a feeling of relief (21) after disclosure 34% of them were anxious of dying soon as opposed to 100% gotten in another study (22). This reduction in anxiety may be due to the fact all the staff working with adolescents in Bamenda 1 health district has been trained on disclosure. After disclosure, most of them felt that they would live a normal live (37.0%), which is in line with another study that reported same (20). On the other hand, some adolescents showed a positive impression as they had already suspected being infected with HIV, or they belief that the medicine should work well and that they could live as long as or even longer than other people, and thought that they were not the only ones living with HIV (52.5%), while others had negative feelings as they thought that they were the only persons living with HIV (46.0.0%), and were not very comfortable concerning HIV and medication(39.0%), thinking that HIV is incurable(27.0).which is in line with another study which reported that upon disclosure, 45.3% had negative feelings .while only 7.9% has positive feelings. with respect to negative feelings, they perceived HIV as an incurable disease and felt difficulty in daily medication for the rest of their life ,and also anxious about dying soon and a sense of isolation, as if being the only person living with HIV, and had a feeling of being stigmatized . On the other hand, some adolescents showed a positive impression as they had already suspected being infected with HIV, or they belief that the medicine should work well and that they could live as long as or even longer than other people(23).

Despite the disappointment upon disclosure, most of the adolescent reported that they continued taking their medications (60%), this is in line with another study that reported that Majority improved and did not change adherence to ART (84.7%) (24). Even though there is a slight difference in the adherence values which may be as a result of the political situation of Bamenda, which makes movements on certain days very impossible. We also found out that, after disclosure, some felt more comfortable talking about HIV with their parents (18.0%), while some blamed their parents (20.0%). Similar results were also reported in other studies even though there are some slight differences in the percentages, it reported that, regarding relationships with parents or primary care givers as a consequence of disclosure 54.2% felt more comfortable talking HIV with their parents/caregivers. While 32% blamed their parents (24). These differences in percentages may be as a result of the cultural norms of the people of Bamenda 1, where it is generally regarded

as a taboo for parents to talk about sexual issues with their children. There is also a lower percentage regarding the children blaming their parents because it is rare to see a child that is coming from a Christian family to talk anyhow to the parents. We also found out that upon disclosure, majority of the adolescents became scared of developing intimate relationships (48.0%), while some isolated themselves from friends (28.0%). This is in line with results from other studies which reported that in relationships with friends or intimate partners, 42.3% became scared of developing intimate relationships and 12.1% isolated themselves from friends (24). There is a slight difference in the values of those that isolated themselves, which may be due to the different societies that the studies were carried out. In this study adolescents thought that isolating themselves may be a method of limiting the spread of the disease to others. This study also reported that, Most of them were not satisfied with the disclosure (70.0%), because they never knew that they could ever be HIV positive, while few were satisfied with the disclosure (30.0%) because they suspected that they had HIV. This ties with another study which reported 7.9% satisfaction (23). This may be due to the fact that they were eager to know why they were taking medicines everyday even when they are not sick. In this study we found out that 73.0% of adolescents that knew their status practiced safe sex which concurs with another study which reported that, for adolescents knowing ones status was associated with safer sex (73.5%) (25). We found out that, some of the adolescents who knew about their HIV seropositive status had not told anybody about it (58.0%), but 38,0% of them had told others. With regards to onward disclosure, 38% of adolescents had told others, meanwhile 58% had not told others. This is not in line with other studies whereby, 11.9% of adolescents had not told anybody, and 81.1% of adolescents had told others (26). 38% of adolescents had told others as opposed to 11.9% in the other study, due to the fact that some adolescents reported that keeping their status as a secret caused them to be stressed up, (29.0%).

30% of them reported that they were ready for the disclosure as opposed to 75% in another study (24). This may be due to the fact that some treatment centers lacked the materials for disclosure. 70% of them were not satisfied as opposed to 46% of them in another work (28). This may be due to the fact that some treatment centers did not have all the necessary disclosure materials. According to the respondents, the following were the advantages of disclosure;

it provides them with the reason for taking medicine everyday (90%), it also improves adherence to ART (80%), It prevents the transmission of HIV (70.0%), It is their basic right (60.0%), and it helps them to know what caused them to be sick most of the time (50.0%) and it also enhances self-care. It is in line with the reports from other works which said that some adolescents regarded knowing one's own HIV status as their basic right, enhance self-care behavior, improves adherence to ART, improves their quality of life, and prevention of HIV transmission to adhere (29). Some of the topics taught before disclosure were; Benefits of adherence (30.0%), how to deal with emotions (15%), Risk of non-adherence (12.5%) and general modes of HIV transmission (10%). duration of taking ART (7.5%), how to get HIV infection (7.5%), how to deal with emotions (7.5%), how to develop hope for the future (12.5%) and how to develop self-esteem (10%). These values greatly differ from other values that were reported in another study, which stated that the following topics were taught to the adolescents before disclosure; topics about HIV and treatment (89%), benefits of adherence (77.4%), duration of taking ART once it begins (73.8%), general modes of HIV transmission (79%), how to get HIV infection (69.5%) (30). This difference in the topics taught could be due to the socio-political situation of the country where some of these adolescents are in schools in different towns and the caregivers/parents just come and collect the drugs and send to their children. We found out that majority of adolescents preferred to be disclosed to at the age of 12 year old (70%). Reasons being that it is their right to know, and that they don't want to remain in darkness for so long. This concurs with some other studies which reported that majority of adolescents recommended the age of 12 as appropriate for adolescents to learn about their HIV serostatus (30,31). In this work, majority of the adolescents preferred to be disclosed to by health care providers (87.5%). Reasons being that they know much about the disease, and that they will tell them the truth. This concurs with another work which reported that adolescents preferred health care providers to disclose rather than their caregivers because they had an opportunity for more accurate information about their disease (29). Majority of them preferred to be disclosed to in a health facility (80%). Reasons being that the health facility looks more real, the health care providers will tell them the right and correct information about their disease and also because health care providers are more knowledgeable and skilled. This concurs with another study where it was reported that adolescents' preferred early disclosure performed in a health care setting (30). It was also reported that adolescents were satisfied with peer support

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groups and that it improved adherence to treatment and increased viral load suppression. It concurs with another research study that showed that facility based peer support was associated with a seven fold increase in the likelihood of aggregate viral load suppression in adolescents when compared with Regional viral load and was also effective in improving retention and adherence to treatment (31). Furthermore, it was reported that majority of the adolescents do participate in their care (67.5%), as opposed to another study where there is the lack of adolescent involvement in decision making(31).

Limitations

The identification of the adolescents with disclosed HIV status was a difficult task.

CONCLUSION

Disclosure is to progressively cause the adolescent to understand his or her HIV status. It is a process. It starts with partial disclosure and gradually progresses to full disclosure. Majority of the adolescents are Prepared for disclosure using the germ theory, counseling, home visits, peer support group and through a gradual release of information concerning their condition. Most of them prefer to be disclosed to at 12 years of age. Majority of the participants had finished primary school. The highest level of education was secondary school .majority of them were not ready for disclosure. Some barriers of disclosure are; fear and stigma experiences, the adolescent is considered to be too young for disclosure and may not be able to keep the HIV status as a secret and the lack of knowledge and skills of disclosure by both the parents and the health workers on disclosure. Some facilitators of disclosure were; the Knowledge of the availability of ART and the view of disclosure as the right of the child. Some negative outcomes of disclosure were Denial/ Depression and Abandonment of medication. some positive outcomes were; improvement in adherence and viral load suppression, enhancement in the stability of the health of the adolescent, improvement on the relationship between the adolescent with their parents, and a better relationship also with the health workers, an increase in the understanding of the disease and a consequent reduction in the cost of the care or the adolescents as he or she is being empowered to come to the clinic alone and follow up his or her care. This will lead to an improvement in the self-

efficacy of the adolescent and will reduce the rate of treatment abandonment and a consequent reduction in viral load and a reduction in the spread of the disease

Perspectives for future studies

Perspectives of adolescents on the use of condoms during sexual intercourse.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST.

The authors declare no conflicts of interest

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